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Corporate Publication of the Scientific Library of KhNMU as a Means of Communication with the University Community: Ten-Year Results

Objective. To analyze the development of the corporate publication «Bibliotherapist» over a ten-year period and to assess its role in fostering the professional growth of the Scientific Library staff of KhNMU. **Methods.** The study draws on a retrospective analysis, content analysis of the publication's issues, and examination of statistical data from the university repository. Special attention is devoted to the stages of development, communication strategies, and student involvement in the publication process. **Results.** The research identifies the key stages in the publication's development and highlights the factors contributing to its growing recognition both in Ukraine and abroad, particularly due to its visibility in the KhNMU repository. The involvement of students in the creating special issues and their role in the editorial board also emphasized. **Conclusions.** The «Bibliotherapist» bulletin has become an effective tool of communication between the library and the university community, as well as with external audiences. The publication contributes to the development of library journalism and reinforces the library's cultural and educational mission.

Keywords: Scientific Library of Kharkiv National Medical University; corporate library publication; "Bibliotherapist" bulletin; publication development; university community; students; communication strategies

Introduction

Relevance of the research topic. The era of digital technologies is rapidly transforming all spheres of human activity, including the library sector. The active implementation of information and communication technologies, the expansion of the information space, and the mediatization of public life are driving the emergence of new formats of library work, in which informational, educational, and communicative functions are closely intertwined. In these circumstances, librarians, similarly to journalists, share common goals: providing reliable, verified information, fostering users' critical thinking, and combating disinformation (Carlson, 2019).

One of the key aspects of digitalization is the development of new models for knowledge dissemination. The concept of "bibliodiversity" defines the variety of scientific ideas, formats, and communication channels, serving as a foundation for the sustainable development of the knowledge ecosystem. In this context, library publishing is viewed as an important factor in supporting open access, diverse formats, and the preservation of academic autonomy in scholarly communication (Ma, Buggle, & O'Neill, 2023).

The full-scale Russian-Ukrainian war has profoundly impacted the organizational processes within institutions, compelling them to adapt to new realities. This also applies to corporate communications, which now not only fulfill management functions but also play a vital role in strengthening resilience during crises, helping to preserve a sense of purpose, realize the organization's mission, and define its place within the framework of human values (Oltarzhevskiy, 2022). Thus, the study of the corporate publication "Bibliotherapist" of the Scientific Library of Kharkiv National Medical University is particularly relevant, as it serves not only as an information resource but also as a platform for professional communication, creativity, and strengthening the educational institution's community.

Statement of the problem. The modern library is increasingly transforming from a traditional intermediary between the reader and the book into an active communicator capable of creating its own information products. Publishing activity has become an integral part of the library's strategic development, ensuring its visibility in the professional environment and enhancing interaction with users. The problem is that the role of corporate library publications as an element of professional communication and a tool for shaping corporate culture remains insufficiently researched.

Analysis of recent research and publications. The COVID-19 pandemic and global social transformations have highlighted the need to rethink the role of libraries in the scholarly ecosystem. Libraries are moving beyond their traditional functions – preserving collections and providing access to literature – toward active participation in scholarly communication, creating conditions for the development of open access publishing services that ensure free and equitable access to knowledge (Komova, 2018).

Considering international studies, the shared mission of journalism and libraries, as emphasized by E. Carlson (2019), lies in providing reliable information and supporting informed communities, which brings librarians closer to media practitioners and opens new avenues for professional interaction. Ma, Buggle, and O'Neill (2023) view "bibliodiversity" as the foundation for developing open models of knowledge dissemination, where library publishing serves as a key instrument for supporting intellectual diversity and the sustainability of the scholarly ecosystem. The evolution of academic library publishing from a subsidiary activity to a fully-fledged platform supporting scholarly communication, highlighted by Sandy and Mattern (2018), confirms the growing role of libraries as independent publishers. Finally, Tracy (2017) examines how library publishing services influence the reading experience, shaping a new culture of information perception in the digital space.

In the Ukrainian scholarly context, Komova (2018) defines the typological structure of corporate publications and underscores their potential as a communication resource that fosters internal organizational cohesion. Kolesnykova and Myrhorodska (2015) analyze the Library Publishing model and demonstrate its effectiveness for university libraries seeking to integrate into the international publishing environment. The practical experience of Kharkiv region libraries, which are actively developing their own publishing initiatives, is highlighted by Zaklinska (2019), emphasizing their role in promoting research findings and supporting internal communication. Particular attention should be given to the observations of Oltarzhevskiy (2022), who, in the context of the war, views corporate communications as a factor of resilience and moral support for the community, further reinforcing the importance of library publications as a tool for social interaction.

Thus, contemporary scholarly research demonstrates that library publishing – both in academic and public libraries – is evolving into a powerful means of communication, professional development, and social cohesion.

In autumn 2024, the Scientific Library of Kharkiv National Medical University (SL KhNMU) celebrated the tenth anniversary of its corporate library publication, "Bibliotherapist". Over this period, the publication has become integral to the library's cultural and educational activities, evolving into a powerful tool for communication between the library and its users. "Bibliotherapist" expands its readership beyond the university community, facilitates the promotion of the library among students and youth, influences personal development, fosters self-growth, and encourages active reading and collaboration.

The aim of this work is to trace the development and summarize the achievements of the corporate publication over the past decade, analyze the contribution of the "Bibliotherapist" bulletin to the activities of the SL KhNMU, the advancement of library journalism, and the

integration of modern media technologies into librarianship. Special attention is paid to the publication amid new challenges and changes in the information environment and society over recent years, as well as its impact on promoting library services and expanding the readership.

Methods

The research was based on a comprehensive approach that combined several methods to thoroughly analysis of the corporate publication "Bibliotherapist" and its communicative role within the university community and beyond.

Retrospective analysis served as the primary method for examining the stages of the publication's establishment. It involved a systematic review of archival materials covering the first decade of its existence, beginning in 2014, well as its subsequent development. The purpose of this analysis was to trace the publication's evolution, conceptual changes, and the transformation of its communication strategies, especially within the context of socio-political changes and challenges during the specified period.

Content analysis was applied for a detailed examination of all issues of the "Bibliotherapist" publication from 2014 to 2024, including current releases. This analysis covered, the thematic scope of sections, the genre diversity of publications (such as articles, interviews, analytical materials, essays, and photographic works), the representation of authors from various university departments, external contributors, and their role in shaping publication's content. Particular attention was paid to the analysis of specific special student issues of "Bibliotherapist" as a creative platform, where all materials were authored exclusively by students, and editorial support and issue production were carried out by librarians. This approach not only enabled the identification and analysis of materials dedicated to student involvement in editorial activities but also allowed for assessing the unique student perspectives on the discussed topics, their participation in content creation, and the influence of the library community fostering young people's creative potential. The analysis of these issues are also provide insights into the mechanisms of their preparation, the student thematic priorities, and the effectiveness of such collaboration. Content analysis further enabled an evaluation of the publication's content alignment with its communication strategies and objectives.

Statistical data analysis was performed by examining information obtained from the university repository. Indicators such as the number of downloads and views of individual issues and articles, readership dynamics, geographical distribution, and data on the activity of authors and readers throughout the entire research period from 2014 to present were investigated. This method enabled a quantitative assessment of the publication's demand and its impact on both the university community and external users during different periods of its existence.

The aforementioned methods, taken together, enabled a comprehensive analysis of the corporate publication "Bibliotherapist," covering both the historical aspects of its establishment and contemporary communication practices, the effectiveness of student involvement, and its overall influence.

Results and Discussion

The idea of creating a corporate publication aimed at expanding the readership originated over ten years ago. However, its practical implementation occurred only after the SL KhNMU staff underwent specialized training at the School of Library Journalism (SLJ) at the Korolenko Kharkiv State Scientific Library. This educational program became a catalyst, providing both

theoretical and practical training for the creation of its own library publication, which has transformed into a dynamic platform for interaction between the library and its readers.

The SL KhNMU staff who first completed the SLJ program in 2014 created a mini-project titled "Reading Doctor" as a result of their training, the second issue of which won first place in the Regional SLJ Project Competition in the same year. These achievements marked the first step toward the development of library journalism at the university and laid the foundation for the further growth of the SL KhNMU corporate publication, which now plays a key role in the library's communication strategy, strengthening its position in the university's information environment and beyond. These staff members subsequently joined the editorial board of the library's forthcoming bulletin.

After a successful start, inspired by the new ideas acquired during the SLJ training, the library team made a decision at a general meeting to create and periodically publish an electronic bulletin titled "Bibliotherapist". The first issue of the SL KhNMU library publication was released on October 1, 2014 – a date considered the starting point of their own corporate media project: the electronic bulletin "Bibliotherapist", available to the public on the library's website <https://libr.knmu.edu.ua/>, (archive <https://repo.knmu.edu.ua/handle/123456789/6941>). Subsequently, a decision was made to print two copies for the library's collection.

The "Bibliotherapist" bulletin is aimed at a broad audience of users, primarily the university community, including youth and students. In the modern context, where young people increasingly turn away from traditional library services due to the rapid development of information and communication technologies and the widespread use of gadgets, the corporate publication becomes an important tool for the library to support self-education processes and foster the development of a conscious, socially active individuals by promoting its own collections and contemporary literature, encouraging active reading, and involving the audience in collaboration as authors, among other activities.

"Bibliotherapist" has transformed into a powerful tool for cultural enlightenment and educational work, contributing to the cultural development and self-realization of the personality, primarily of youth, thereby reinforcing the library's role as a hub of knowledge and enlightenment in the university environment. It serves as a living connection between the library and student community, especially amid contemporary challenges.

One of the major challenges for the library leadership has been providing continuous training for staff in the fundamentals of library journalism. This task has been carried out almost every year: between 2014 and 2024, 18 SL KhNMU staff members successfully completed the SLJ program, representing 25% of the library's pre-war personnel. Some of them, consistently improving their qualifications, participated in the School multiple times. Almost all received prizes and diplomas of various levels, indicating a high level of training and strong interest in the development of library journalism. The SLJ participants acquired comprehensive knowledge of editing theory and practice, mastered the various stages involved in preparing and producing library newspapers, and explored the genres of library journalism along with their evolution under the influence of media convergence. They also familiarized themselves with latest trends in new media and explored opportunities for their application in library practice. Special attention was given to cross-media journalism in libraries, the development of in-house library channels, and the use of online services to promote library resources and services.

Many ideas proposed during the training have already been successfully implemented in the columns of the "Bibliotherapist" bulletin. Several author columns established by SLJ graduates have emerged such as "Ascorbic Acid for the Soul" (2015), "Literary Note" (2016), "Founders" (2017), "A Journey with a Writer" (2017). They became an example of applying these skills, an important platform for self-realization through literary word, showcasing both the authors'

personal talents and their contribution to the cultural enrichment of the readership. The efforts of the School's graduates to advance the publication reflect their strong professional skills and have a positive influence on the information environment. However, author columns are created not only by SLJ graduates but also by experienced library professionals. Among these are "Library Treasury: Through the Pages of Rare and Valuable Editions" (2015), "Medical Kharkiv" (2019), "Ailments of the Great" (2021), and others – all of which have been launched and regularly updated with engaging content. In addition to author columns, other sections are also created and contributed to by various authors, in particular, representatives of the university, colleagues from other higher education institutions and libraries – a flexible content development system that responds to current topics and reader interests.

A special focus of the editorial board's work is maintaining a cloud-based editorial portfolio for gathering and storing materials for future issues. This portfolio is a key component of the preparation process for each new issue, as it allows the editorial team to keep track of all potential publications, ensuring both the planning and gradual development of thematic content. Collected articles, reviews, and other materials are sorted and go through internal editorial processing to be refined before publication in the next issue. Each library department has designated persons responsible for providing materials for the "Bibliotherapist" bulletin, who assist in building the editorial portfolio.

During the full-scale Russian military aggression against Ukraine, SLJ graduates of the 2023-2025 cohorts acquired new competence, including documenting, memorializing, and recording wartime events, and also the possibilities of using artificial intelligence (AI) in library practice. In 2025, representatives of the Scientific Library of KhNMU took part in the XIV All-Ukrainian Online School of Library Journalist, which was held under the motto "Artificial intelligence in library media: trend or necessity?" Within the framework of professional training, the prospects of integrating AI tools into the process of creating library content, including visual, informational, and analytical content, were considered, and the ethical and practical aspects of its application in the field of library journalism were also discussed. They also became familiar with different modern communication platforms such as TikTok and Telegram, considering their potential for libraries, especially through book blogging. This knowledge and these skills not only broadened the professional horizons of the library staff but also contributed to adapting librarianship to today's challenges.

The first issue of the "Bibliotherapist" bulletin was only four pages long, marking the initial stage of the publication's development. Today, "Bibliotherapist" is a full-fledged periodical consisting of 20-28 pages. Throughout its existence, the publication has undergone three major rebranding stages, involving changes not only to the cover design but also to fonts, overall layout, and content formatting: January 2016 – the table of contents was moved to the front cover; January 2018 – the title font was changed, and the table of contents was relocated from the cover to the second page; January 2022 – the overall content presentation concept was completely revised, along with updates to fonts, layout, and other design elements. Thus, the early issues had a simple cover, which later evolved into a modern design, including full photographic images created by the bulletin's authors. Typography in previous issues has been updated to improve readability and visual appeal. The overall design of the bulletin has progressed from a simple layout to a complex and professionally designed format featuring contemporary graphic elements that enhance both its informational value and aesthetic appeal. This development process demonstrates significant progress in approaches to design and information presentation. Rebranding, new design approaches, increased publication volume, expanded sections, and improved content quality reflect the growing professionalism of library journalists as editors and content creators (Fig. 1).

MANAGEMENT AND MARKETING AT THE UNIVERSITY LIBRARIES

Fig. 1.

The sustained refinement of these aspects results from the contributions of the SL KhNMU staff, primarily SLJ graduates, whose experience and achievements in library journalism help shape a modern and high-quality information environment. Supporting the training and professional development of librarians, especially young specialists, is one of the key policy priorities of SL KhNMU management. This has significantly contributed to the success and popularity of the "Biblioterapist" publication, which currently comprises 129 main issues.

Continuous training and an innovative approach to producing a corporate publication have led to the library's recognition within the university community, especially among students, whose engagement is growing. In addition to librarians, various members of the university community – including students, teachers, and other staff – are involved in creating the "Biblioterapist" bulletin. On its pages, they share stories about the everyday and festive moments of university life, medical dynasties, fascinating stories about medicine and its notable figures, and express their inspiration through poetry, prose, painting, and more. Indeed, members of the university community have contributed to sections such as: Reading with Flavor, My Family – My Roots, Students Create, Student Humor, Inspiration, Art Gallery, A Soul Wounded by War, and others.

Over time, cooperation with the student government led to an important decision in 2017 – launching special issues of "Biblioterapist" primarily aimed at the student audience. This allowed students to actively engage in the creative process as authors, while librarians retained their role as editors and publishers. So far, 22 special issues have been released, and this initiative continues to develop. Involving students in the creation of the corporate publication has become a strategic step for the library, aimed at strengthening engagement with young readers. The student issues of "Biblioterapist" serve not only as motivation for creative self-realization but also as an important tool for integrating youth into the literary environment and as another communication channel with the library.

The SL KhNMU implements a modern strategy to promote the corporate publication "Biblioterapist," which encompasses various media tools to effectively deliver content to the target audience. In particular, the library utilizes its own website and the university's site, actively maintains a presence on social media, publishes video announcements on its YouTube and TikTok channels, and places announcements with QR codes to provide quick access to new issues of "Biblioterapist" and its archive.

The success of the corporate publication "Bibliotherapist" enabled its editors to take on the role of tutors for SLJ participants. This indicates that the growing popularity of the publication and the editorial skills acquired in the process have become an important milestone in the development of library journalism at SL KhNMU and the university as a whole.

The evolution from learners to tutors and workshop leaders, in partnership with the SLJ, clearly demonstrates how training and active involvement in library journalism can transform School participants into experienced professionals. This process highlights how involvement in creating and promoting a corporate publication provides library specialists with deep knowledge and professional skills which they then use to train and mentor other professionals.

The reputation of the corporate publication "Bibliotherapist" extends beyond Ukraine and has gained recognition abroad. Statistical analysis of the KhNMU Repository data shows that the publication is actively read not only in Ukraine but also in various countries around the world. This is confirmed by download and view statistics from foreign IP addresses, reflecting the growing international interest in the content of "Bibliotherapist". For example, over the last year, the top countries from which the bulletin was accessed, in addition to Ukraine, included Germany, Hungary, France, New Zealand, Sweden, the United States, Ireland, Singapore, and others. Over the period from 2014 to 2024, the archive of the corporate bulletin "Bibliotherapist", hosted in the KhNMU Repository, received over 30,000 views. Considering the publication's popular science and cultural-educational nature, its placement on an academic platform, and its broad target audience, this figure indicates a sustained reflects in the bulletin's content, high demand, and positive dissemination dynamic both within the university community and beyond.

Consequently, the statistical data obtained confirm that "Bibliotherapist" fullfills not only an informational and educational function but also effectively realizes the potential of a library-based media outlet as an effective tool for international cultural communication.

In October 2024, on the occasion of the 10th anniversary of the corporate publication "Bibliotherapist", its editorial board was honored with a Certificate of Appreciation from the Kharkiv Regional Department (branch) of All-Ukrainian Non-Government Organization Ukrainian Library Association for its high level of professionalism and significant contribution to the development of library journalism in the Kharkiv region.

Conclusions

In summary, the success of the corporate media project "Bibliotherapist" stems from a strategic approach to the professional training of library staff, involving continuous knowledge acquisition and exchange, encouragement of creative activity and content relevance, leveraging new media technologies. This contributes not only to the development of librarians' personal competencies but also to fostering effective communication and collaboration within the entire university community. Therefore, the library's strategic approach to publication promotion and specialist training exemplifies successful practice in library journalism and may be considered by other teams striving to achieve meaningful results in this work.

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Корпоративне видання Наукової бібліотеки ХНМУ як засіб комунікації з університетською спільнотою: підсумки першого десятиріччя

Мета статті – проаналізувати розвиток корпоративного видання «Бібліотерапевт» за десять років та оцінити його роль у професійному зростанні співробітників Наукової бібліотеки ХНМУ. **Методика.** Дослідження базується на ретроспективному аналізі, контент-аналізі випусків видання та вивченні статистичних даних з університетського репозитарію. Особливу увагу приділено етапам становлення, комунікаційним стратегіям і залученню студентів до видання. **Результати.** Виокремлено ключові етапи розвитку видання, окреслено чинники зростання його популярності в Україні та за кордоном, зокрема завдяки представленості в репозитарії ХНМУ. Розкрито участь студентів у створенні спецвипусків та їхню роль у діяльності редколегії. **Висновки.** Бюлетень «Бібліотерапевт» став ефективним інструментом комунікації між бібліотекою та університетською спільнотою, а також з аудиторією поза її межами. Видання сприяє розвитку бібліотечної журналістики та посиленню культурно-просвітницької місії бібліотеки.

Ключові слова: Наукова бібліотека Харківського національного медичного університету; корпоративне бібліотечне видання; бюлетень «Бібліотерапевт»; розвиток видання; університетська спільнота; студенти; комунікаційні стратегії

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